

Family Dynamics and Women's Inheritance Rights: A Case Study of District Mardan

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Abstract: *Women's inheritance rights remain one of the most contested dimensions of gender equality in Pakistan despite constitutional guarantees, Islamic injunctions, and statutory protections. Although women are legally recognized as rightful heirs, many continue to face substantial obstacles in exercising these rights within the family. This study examines how family dynamics shape women's access to inherited property in District Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Using a qualitative case study approach, the research draws upon interviews conducted with women, legal practitioners, and relevant stakeholders to explore the ways in which familial relationships influence inheritance decisions. The study finds that women's deprivation of inheritance is less a consequence of inadequate legal provisions than of intra-family power relations. Brothers frequently assume exclusive control over inherited property, while emotional pressure, fear of damaging family relationships, dependence on natal families, and concern for family honour discourage women from claiming their legal shares. Parents and extended family members often reinforce these practices through customary expectations that prioritize family cohesion over women's legal entitlements. The findings further reveal that lengthy legal procedures and institutional barriers discourage women from pursuing legal remedies when family negotiations fail. Consequently, legal rights often remain symbolic rather than practically enforceable. The study concludes that improving women's inheritance rights requires interventions that extend beyond legislative reform to address family-level decision-making processes, legal awareness, and institutional support mechanisms. Strengthening the implementation of existing laws while transforming social attitudes within families is essential for ensuring that women's inheritance rights become a lived reality rather than a formal legal entitlement.*

Keywords: *Women's inheritance rights, family dynamics, property rights, qualitative research, District Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.*

Introduction**Introduction**

Women's ownership of property is widely recognised as a fundamental determinant of economic security, social status, and decision-making power within the household. In agrarian societies, ownership of agricultural land is particularly significant because it provides not only economic stability but also social recognition and influence within family and community structures (Haque et al., 2020). In Pakistan, where agriculture remains one of the principal sectors of the economy, land ownership continues to shape patterns of wealth distribution, family authority, and gender relations. According to the World Bank Group (2019),

approximately 63.6% of Pakistan's population resides in rural areas, while women constitute 48.8% of the country's total population. Despite their substantial contribution to agricultural production and household livelihoods, women's ownership and control of inherited property remain disproportionately low.

Inheritance represents one of the principal mechanisms through which property is transferred across generations. Legally, inheritance refers to the transfer of the estate of a deceased person to his or her lawful heirs in accordance with prescribed legal principles (Accurate and Reliable Dictionary, 2008; Black's Law Dictionary, 1999; Lloyd & Derrett, 1965). Similarly, land ownership denotes the legally recognised authority to acquire, possess, utilise, manage, and transfer land while exercising exclusive rights over its use (Johnston, 2018). These legal concepts are particularly important in societies where agricultural land constitutes the primary source of income and family wealth.

Islam introduced one of the earliest comprehensive systems recognising women's inheritance rights. The Holy Qur'an explicitly grants women a fixed and obligatory share in inherited property regardless of the amount of the estate. Surah Al-Nisa (4:7) clearly states that both men and women are entitled to a prescribed share of what parents and close relatives leave behind. Additional verses of the same chapter further specify the inheritance shares of daughters, mothers, wives, and sisters, thereby establishing a comprehensive legal framework that recognises women as independent property owners. Unlike pre-Islamic customs that excluded women from inheritance, Islamic law treats inheritance as a legal entitlement rather than a discretionary favour bestowed by male relatives.

These principles are reinforced by international human rights instruments. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) recognises every individual's right to own property and prohibits arbitrary deprivation of property. Likewise, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW, 1979) obliges member states to eliminate discrimination against women in matters relating to property ownership and inheritance. Pakistan has also incorporated these commitments within its constitutional framework. Articles 23 and 24 of the Constitution of Pakistan (1973) guarantee every citizen the right to acquire, hold, and dispose of property, while Article 25 affirms equality before the law and prohibits discrimination on the basis of sex (Naznin, 2018). More recently, legislative initiatives such as the Enforcement of Women's Property Rights Act, 2020 and the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Women Property Rights Act, 2019 have been introduced to strengthen institutional protection for women's property rights.

Despite these constitutional guarantees, Islamic injunctions, and statutory reforms, the implementation of women's inheritance rights remains inconsistent, particularly in rural areas of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Existing evidence indicates that legal deprivation is rarely caused by shortcomings in legislation alone. Instead, the denial of women's inheritance frequently occurs within the family, where inheritance decisions are shaped by social expectations, customary practices, and unequal power relations (Haque et al., 2020). Women may possess a legally

recognised right to inherit property, yet the exercise of that right often depends upon negotiations with brothers, parents, and other influential family members rather than the formal application of inheritance law.

Unlike legal disputes involving unrelated parties, inheritance disputes emerge within close family relationships where emotional attachment, kinship obligations, and concerns regarding family honour significantly influence decision-making. In many households, brothers assume control over inherited property following the death of parents and expect sisters to relinquish their legal shares voluntarily. Such practices are frequently justified through cultural beliefs that agricultural land should remain under male ownership to preserve family assets or prevent fragmentation of ancestral property. Consequently, many women encounter considerable pressure to sacrifice their legal entitlement in favour of maintaining harmonious family relationships.

Despite extensive legal protection, empirical evidence suggests that women's inheritance rights in Pakistan remain largely unrealized in practice. Previous studies have shown that the denial of inheritance rarely occurs because of deficiencies in Islamic jurisprudence or statutory law. Instead, the principal barriers emerge within the family, where customary expectations, patriarchal authority, and unequal power relations shape decisions regarding the distribution of inherited property (Ahmed, 2010; Mumtaz, 2005). Consequently, women's legal entitlement often becomes secondary to informal family arrangements that prioritize the interests of male heirs.

Within Pakhtun society, inheritance is not merely a legal process but also a social institution embedded in kinship relations. Family members collectively influence decisions regarding land ownership, succession, and property transfer. Brothers frequently assume responsibility for managing inherited land following the death of parents and often become the principal decision-makers regarding its distribution. In many cases, sisters are expected to relinquish their lawful shares voluntarily to preserve family unity and prevent the fragmentation of ancestral property. Such expectations are reinforced through emotional appeals, social obligations, and deeply rooted beliefs concerning family honour. As a result, women frequently encounter considerable pressure to prioritize harmonious family relationships over their legally recognized economic rights.

Literature Review

The literature further indicates that parental attitudes significantly influence inheritance outcomes. Parents may transfer property to sons during their lifetime, postpone discussions regarding inheritance, or assume that daughters have already received their share through dowry and marriage-related expenditures. Although these practices possess considerable social acceptance in many communities, they have no equivalent status under Islamic inheritance law, which clearly distinguishes inheritance from voluntary gifts or marital arrangements (Ahmed, 2010). Consequently, informal family practices frequently produce unequal outcomes that disadvantage female heirs despite comprehensive legal protection.

Another important dimension concerns women's continuing dependence upon their natal families after marriage. Even after establishing separate households, many women continue to

rely upon parents and brothers for emotional support, mediation during marital disputes, and financial assistance in times of need. This dependence influences women's willingness to assert inheritance claims because pursuing legal action against brothers may permanently damage family relationships. Participants in the present study repeatedly emphasized that women often choose silence over confrontation, viewing the preservation of family cohesion as more valuable than securing inherited property. Such decisions should therefore be understood not as voluntary relinquishment of legal rights but as outcomes shaped by unequal family power relations.

Although legal remedies are available through courts and administrative institutions, their practical effectiveness remains constrained by lengthy judicial procedures, bureaucratic complexities, and limited institutional accessibility. Ahmed (2010) argues that Pakistan's constitutional and statutory framework provides adequate legal recognition of women's inheritance rights; however, implementation remains weak due to limited enforcement and the persistence of customary practices. Similarly, international commitments under CEDAW emphasize the obligation of states to eliminate discrimination in matters relating to property ownership and inheritance, yet the practical realization of these commitments continues to encounter substantial social and institutional challenges (International, 2009; Mumtaz, 2005).

District Mardan provides an appropriate context for examining these issues because it reflects many of the social, cultural, and economic characteristics associated with rural Pakhtun society. While legal awareness regarding women's rights has gradually increased, inheritance disputes continue to be resolved predominantly through family negotiations rather than formal legal mechanisms. This creates an important opportunity to examine how family dynamics influence women's ability to exercise rights that are already guaranteed under Islamic law and Pakistani legislation.

Unlike previous studies that have primarily emphasized legal frameworks or broader cultural traditions, the present study focuses specifically on the role of family dynamics in shaping women's inheritance experiences. By examining relationships among brothers, sisters, parents, and extended family members, the study seeks to explain how intra-family interactions facilitate or obstruct the realization of women's inheritance rights. In doing so, it contributes to a more nuanced understanding of the persistent gap between legal entitlement and practical implementation in District Mardan.

Women's inheritance rights have attracted considerable scholarly attention across legal, sociological, and gender studies because ownership of property is closely associated with economic empowerment, social status, and personal autonomy. Although many countries have introduced legal mechanisms to protect women's inheritance rights, the practical realization of these rights continues to be constrained by family structures, customary practices, and institutional weaknesses. Existing literature demonstrates that inheritance disputes cannot be understood solely through legal frameworks; rather, they emerge from the interaction of family relationships, patriarchal authority, cultural expectations, and administrative systems (Agarwal, 1998; Deere & León, 2001).

In Pakistan, inheritance rights are governed simultaneously by Islamic law, constitutional provisions, and statutory legislation. The Constitution guarantees every citizen the right to acquire, hold, and dispose of property while prohibiting unlawful deprivation of property (Ahmed, 2010). Similarly, Islamic inheritance law prescribes fixed shares for female heirs and recognizes women as independent owners of inherited property. International commitments, including the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), further reinforce the state's responsibility to ensure women's equal access to property rights (International, 2009). Despite these legal protections, women continue to experience substantial barriers in exercising their inheritance rights, particularly within rural communities where customary norms frequently prevail over formal legal institutions (Mumtaz, 2005).

A significant body of literature attributes women's deprivation of inheritance to patriarchal family systems that concentrate authority over land and productive assets in the hands of male relatives. Liberal feminist scholars argue that gender inequality is sustained through institutional arrangements that deny women equal opportunities to exercise their legal rights and personal autonomy (Cudd, 2006; Tong, 2016). According to this perspective, the existence of legal rights alone is insufficient if social institutions fail to enforce them effectively. Women's dependence on male family members often limits their capacity to claim property that is legally theirs.

Family relationships occupy a central position in inheritance decisions. Unlike many legal disputes that involve unrelated parties, inheritance claims arise within intimate family networks where emotional obligations, kinship ties, and long-term relationships influence decision-making. Kamal (1999) argues that although women may legally inherit property, effective control frequently remains with male relatives who manage transactions, cultivation, and disposal of land. Consequently, legal ownership does not necessarily translate into actual possession or decision-making authority. This distinction between formal ownership and practical control illustrates the importance of examining family dynamics rather than legal provisions alone.

Research conducted in Pakistan consistently demonstrates that brothers play a decisive role in determining whether sisters receive their rightful inheritance. Women's inheritance is frequently treated as negotiable rather than obligatory, with sisters expected to relinquish their legal shares voluntarily in favour of their brothers. Mehdi (2002) observes that women's names often appear in official inheritance records without corresponding transfer of effective ownership, indicating that legal documentation alone does not guarantee access to inherited assets. Instead, family negotiations frequently result in women surrendering their inheritance under social or emotional pressure.

One explanation for this phenomenon lies in women's continuing dependence upon their natal families after marriage. Although married women establish separate households, they often continue to rely on parents and brothers during periods of marital conflict, financial hardship, or personal crisis. This dependence creates an unequal bargaining position in which women

hesitate to assert inheritance claims that may jeopardize family relationships. Kamal (1999) notes that women frequently surrender inherited property because maintaining supportive relationships with brothers is considered more valuable than securing ownership of land. Such decisions are rarely voluntary in the strict legal sense but instead reflect broader social expectations governing family solidarity.

Parents also influence inheritance outcomes through informal distribution practices and gendered expectations regarding family responsibilities. Traditional assumptions that sons will remain responsible for agricultural production and elderly parents encourage unequal allocation of family resources long before formal inheritance procedures begin. In many cases, daughters are expected to benefit from dowry or marital support rather than inherited land, despite the distinction between these two forms of property recognized in both law and Islamic jurisprudence. Deere and León (2001) argue that dowry cannot be considered a substitute for inheritance because inheritance constitutes a legal entitlement rather than a discretionary family gift.

The persistence of these practices reflects broader patriarchal conceptions of property ownership. Bennett (1981) estimates that women own less than two percent of titled land globally, illustrating the enduring gender imbalance in property ownership. Property ownership provides women with economic security, bargaining power, and protection against vulnerability; therefore, denying inheritance has consequences extending well beyond ownership itself. Agarwal (1998) similarly argues that access to land significantly strengthens women's social position by increasing economic independence and reducing dependence on male relatives.

Comparative studies conducted outside Pakistan reveal similar patterns. Brown and Chowdhury (2002) found that women in rural West Bengal rarely own agricultural land despite legal entitlement, while Quisumbing et al. (2004) demonstrated that increased female participation in agricultural production contributes positively to women's ownership of inherited land. Conversely, Matashane and Marite (2005) observed that discrimination in agricultural inheritance persists in Lesotho despite legal reforms intended to improve women's property rights. Deere and León (2003) likewise concluded that gender disparities in land ownership throughout Latin America continue because inheritance systems remain strongly influenced by male-centred family traditions.

Besides family relationships, institutional barriers further complicate women's efforts to secure inherited property. Women frequently encounter lengthy legal procedures, complex administrative requirements, inadequate legal assistance, and bureaucratic delays when seeking formal enforcement of their inheritance rights. Bozeman (1993) describes such institutional inefficiencies as characteristics of bureaucratic systems that create unnecessary procedural burdens for citizens seeking public services. These obstacles disproportionately affect women because many already face financial dependence and limited mobility before initiating legal proceedings.

Women's limited awareness of inheritance procedures also contributes to unequal outcomes. Tirmazi (1999) argues that insufficient knowledge of land registration systems, legal documentation, and property transactions prevents many women from effectively exercising ownership rights even when these rights are legally recognized. Limited mobility further restricts women's ability to visit government offices, attend court hearings, or supervise inherited agricultural land. Consequently, male relatives often continue exercising practical control over property that legally belongs to women.

Existing scholarship therefore suggests that women's inheritance rights are shaped by multiple interconnected factors operating simultaneously within families, communities, and institutions. However, much of the available literature has examined legal frameworks, customary practices, or gender inequality in broader terms. Comparatively less attention has been devoted to understanding how everyday family relationships influence women's decisions to claim, negotiate, or relinquish inherited property. Since inheritance disputes originate within families rather than courts, examining family dynamics provides important insight into the mechanisms through which legal rights are either realized or denied.

This study addresses this gap by focusing specifically on the role of family relationships in shaping women's inheritance experiences in District Mardan. Rather than treating family members merely as participants in inheritance disputes, the study examines how interactions among parents, brothers, sisters, spouses, and extended relatives influence women's ability to exercise rights that are already recognized under Islamic and statutory law. Through this perspective, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of the relationship between family power structures and the practical realization of women's inheritance rights.

Research Questions

How do family dynamics influence women's access to inheritance rights in District Mardan?

What role do brothers, parents, and extended family members play in shaping women's inheritance decisions?

Research Objectives

To examine the influence of family dynamics on women's inheritance rights in District Mardan.

To explore the role of brothers, parents, and extended family members in inheritance-related decision-making.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative research approach using a case study design to explore the influence of family dynamics on women's inheritance rights in District Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The qualitative approach was considered appropriate because it facilitates an in-depth understanding of participants' lived experiences, perceptions, and social interactions that cannot be adequately captured through quantitative methods (Creswell, 2014; Yin, 2014). Primary data were collected through semi-structured interviews with women, legal practitioners, government officials, and other stakeholders directly involved in inheritance-

related issues. Participants were selected through purposive sampling to ensure that individuals possessing relevant knowledge and practical experience were included in the study. The interviews were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis, allowing recurring patterns and themes to emerge from the participants' narratives (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Ethical considerations, including informed consent, confidentiality, voluntary participation, and anonymity of respondents, were observed throughout the research process.

Discussion and Analysis

Family Power Structures and the Denial of Women's Inheritance Rights

The findings indicate that family relationships constitute the primary context within which women's inheritance rights are either recognized or denied. Although Islamic law and Pakistan's legal framework clearly establish women's entitlement to inherit property, inheritance decisions in District Mardan are predominantly negotiated within families rather than implemented through formal legal procedures. Consequently, brothers, parents, and other senior male relatives exercise considerable influence over the distribution of inherited property, often determining whether women receive their lawful shares.

The interviews reveal that brothers occupy a dominant position in inheritance-related decision-making. Participants consistently described brothers as the principal custodians of family land following the death of parents. Rather than viewing inheritance as a legal obligation, many families considered land a collective family asset that should remain under male control to preserve agricultural productivity and maintain the continuity of the paternal lineage. Within this context, sisters were frequently expected to relinquish their legal entitlement voluntarily in favour of their brothers. Several respondents explained that women were discouraged from demanding inheritance because such claims were perceived as challenging the authority of male family members and threatening established family relationships.

The findings further demonstrate that women's bargaining position within the family is considerably weaker than that of men. Although female heirs possess legally recognized ownership rights, practical control over inherited property remains concentrated among male relatives. Participants reported that brothers usually managed land registration, cultivation, leasing arrangements, and financial transactions associated with inherited property. As a result, women's legal ownership often existed only in principle while effective control remained with male family members. This distinction between formal ownership and practical possession illustrates that inheritance disputes extend beyond legal entitlement and reflect broader patterns of gendered authority operating within the household.

These findings support previous scholarship suggesting that patriarchal family structures continue to shape women's access to productive assets despite legal reforms (Agarwal, 1998; Deere & León, 2001). Liberal feminist perspectives similarly argue that legal equality alone cannot eliminate gender inequality when social institutions continue to reproduce unequal power relations (Cudd, 2006; Tong, 2016). The findings of this study reinforce this argument

by demonstrating that inheritance decisions are embedded within family power structures where brothers exercise significant influence over women's economic rights.

Emotional Pressure, Family Honour, and Women's Silence

One of the most significant findings emerging from the interviews concerns the role of emotional pressure in discouraging women from claiming inheritance. Participants repeatedly emphasized that women often refrain from demanding their legal share not because they are unaware of their rights but because they fear damaging relationships with their brothers and other close relatives. Maintaining family unity was consistently described as a moral responsibility placed upon women, particularly after the death of parents when sibling relationships become increasingly important.

Many respondents explained that inheritance disputes are viewed as family conflicts rather than legal disagreements. Women who pursue their inheritance through formal legal channels frequently face criticism from relatives and community members, who interpret litigation against brothers as an act of disobedience or disrespect. Consequently, women often experience emotional coercion to withdraw inheritance claims in order to preserve family harmony. Participants indicated that sisters were regularly advised by elders and relatives to avoid legal action, even when they believed that their rights had been violated.

The interviews also suggest that the concept of family honour plays a significant role in shaping inheritance decisions. In Pakhtun society, family cohesion and mutual support are highly valued social ideals. Women who insist upon receiving inherited land may be portrayed as prioritizing personal financial interests over collective family welfare. Such perceptions generate considerable psychological pressure, encouraging women to remain silent despite experiencing economic injustice. Several participants noted that many women willingly surrendered inherited property because maintaining lifelong relationships with brothers was considered more valuable than acquiring ownership of land.

Fear of social isolation further reinforces this pattern. Married women frequently continue to rely upon their natal families for emotional support and assistance during periods of marital difficulty. Initiating inheritance litigation against brothers may jeopardize this support system, increasing women's vulnerability in other aspects of life. As a result, inheritance decisions are often influenced by emotional considerations rather than legal principles. This demonstrates that family relationships function simultaneously as sources of protection and mechanisms through which women's legal rights are constrained.

These findings are consistent with previous studies emphasizing that women's dependence on natal families frequently discourages them from asserting inheritance rights (Kamal, 1999; Mehdi, 2002). The results therefore suggest that improving legal enforcement alone may not substantially increase women's access to inherited property unless broader family attitudes toward women's economic rights also change.

Parental Decisions and the Reproduction of Gender Inequality

The interviews reveal that inequality in inheritance frequently begins before formal succession takes place. Participants explained that parents often make informal property arrangements during their lifetime that favour sons over daughters. Agricultural land was commonly transferred to male children before the death of parents, leaving little property available for equitable distribution under Islamic inheritance principles. Such arrangements were frequently justified on the grounds that sons would remain responsible for agricultural production and the long-term care of elderly parents.

Another recurring theme concerned the widespread perception that dowry constitutes a substitute for inheritance. Several respondents observed that families often believe daughters have already received their share of parental wealth through marriage-related expenditures, including dowry, household goods, jewellery, or wedding ceremonies. Consequently, daughters are expected to forgo subsequent inheritance claims in favour of their brothers. However, participants acknowledged that these practices have no legal basis and frequently result in women's permanent exclusion from productive family assets.

The findings further indicate that parents rarely communicate openly about inheritance arrangements before their death. The absence of transparent family discussions often creates opportunities for misunderstanding, manipulation, and unequal distribution among surviving siblings. In many cases, brothers assume responsibility for administering inherited property without meaningful consultation with their sisters. Women consequently become dependent upon the goodwill of male relatives rather than relying upon clearly documented inheritance arrangements.

These findings support the argument advanced by Deere and León (2001) that dowry should not be regarded as an alternative to inheritance because inheritance represents a legally protected property right rather than a discretionary family gift. The study also demonstrates how gender inequality is reproduced across generations through informal family practices that operate alongside formal legal institutions.

Family Dynamics and the Limits of Legal Protection

Although Pakistan has established constitutional, statutory, and religious safeguards to protect women's inheritance rights, the findings of this study demonstrate that legal protection alone is insufficient to ensure women's effective access to inherited property. Participants consistently indicated that legal mechanisms are generally considered only after family negotiations have failed. Consequently, the realization of inheritance rights depends less upon the existence of legal provisions than upon women's willingness and ability to challenge family decisions.

A recurring theme in the interviews was the reluctance of women to initiate legal proceedings against close relatives. Participants explained that litigation involving brothers was widely perceived as socially undesirable because it transformed private family disagreements into public disputes. Many women preferred to tolerate economic deprivation rather than face the

emotional consequences of prolonged legal conflict with family members. Respondents further observed that women who pursued inheritance claims through the courts frequently experienced criticism from relatives and community members, who interpreted legal action as a violation of cultural expectations regarding family loyalty and respect for elder male relatives.

The findings also reveal that institutional barriers reinforce the influence of family pressure. Respondents described inheritance litigation as lengthy, expensive, and procedurally complex. Delays in court proceedings, repeated visits to government offices, and complicated documentation requirements discouraged many women from pursuing formal legal remedies. Even where women possessed sufficient legal knowledge, the practical costs associated with litigation often outweighed the anticipated benefits of claiming inherited property. Consequently, family negotiations remained the preferred method of dispute resolution despite their tendency to favour male family members.

Another important finding concerns the interaction between legal awareness and family decision-making. Several participants indicated that women increasingly understand their inheritance rights under Islamic law and Pakistani legislation. However, awareness alone rarely translated into successful inheritance claims because decisions continued to be shaped by family relationships rather than legal knowledge. Women frequently acknowledged their legal entitlement while simultaneously expressing unwillingness to challenge brothers or parents. This suggests that information campaigns, although important, cannot independently eliminate gender disparities in inheritance unless accompanied by broader changes in family attitudes and institutional accessibility.

The study therefore demonstrates that legal institutions operate within a broader social environment where family authority frequently supersedes statutory protections. Courts and administrative agencies remain important mechanisms for enforcing women's rights, yet their effectiveness is constrained when women perceive legal action as threatening family relationships or personal security. The findings support previous research arguing that the implementation gap in women's inheritance rights reflects both institutional limitations and deeply embedded family power structures (Mumtaz, 2005; Ahmed, 2010).

Taken together, the four analytical themes indicate that family dynamics constitute the central mechanism through which women's inheritance rights are negotiated, restricted, or denied. Brothers exercise significant influence over inheritance decisions, parents often reproduce gendered patterns of property distribution, emotional obligations discourage women from asserting legal claims, and institutional barriers reinforce family authority by making legal remedies difficult to pursue. These interconnected processes explain why constitutional guarantees and Islamic principles have not translated into equal access to inherited property for many women in District Mardan.

Findings

The findings of this study demonstrate that family dynamics play a decisive role in determining whether women are able to exercise their inheritance rights in District Mardan. Although

Islamic law and Pakistan's legal framework recognize women as legitimate heirs, inheritance decisions remain primarily governed by intra-family relationships and customary practices rather than formal legal principles.

The study found that brothers were the most influential actors in inheritance-related decision-making. Following the death of parents, brothers commonly assumed responsibility for managing inherited property and often expected sisters to relinquish their legal shares voluntarily. Women's dependence on harmonious relationships with their brothers reduced their willingness to challenge these expectations.

Another major finding concerns the influence of emotional pressure within families. Women frequently avoided inheritance disputes because they feared damaging relationships with siblings, creating conflict among relatives, or undermining family honour. Maintaining family cohesion was often considered more important than obtaining economic benefits through inherited property. Consequently, many women surrendered their legal rights without formal objection.

The findings further reveal that parental decisions contribute to the continuation of unequal inheritance practices. Property transferred to sons during parents' lifetime, together with the widespread belief that dowry represents a substitute for inheritance, reinforced gender inequality before formal succession occurred. These practices limited women's opportunities to claim inherited assets despite legal recognition of their rights.

The study also identified important institutional challenges that interacted with family dynamics. Lengthy court procedures, bureaucratic complexity, financial costs, and procedural delays discouraged women from pursuing legal remedies after unsuccessful family negotiations. Even women who possessed knowledge of their legal rights often considered litigation a last resort because of its potential social and emotional consequences.

Overall, the findings indicate that women's deprivation of inheritance is not primarily the result of inadequate legal provisions but rather the combined influence of family power structures, emotional obligations, customary expectations, and institutional barriers. These factors collectively create an environment in which legal rights exist formally but remain difficult to realize in practice.

Conclusion

This study examined the influence of family dynamics on women's inheritance rights in District Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Drawing upon qualitative evidence, the research demonstrates that the implementation of women's inheritance rights is shaped less by deficiencies in law than by the operation of family relationships and intra-household power structures. While Islamic law and Pakistan's legal framework provide clear protection for female heirs, these protections

frequently encounter resistance within the family, where inheritance decisions are influenced by patriarchal authority, emotional obligations, and customary expectations.

The findings reveal that brothers occupy a dominant position in inheritance-related decision-making, while parents and extended family members often reinforce unequal patterns of property distribution through informal practices and gendered expectations. Emotional pressure, concern for family honour, and fear of disrupting relationships discourage many women from asserting their legal rights even when they are aware of them. Institutional challenges, including lengthy legal procedures and bureaucratic obstacles, further reduce women's willingness to pursue formal enforcement mechanisms, allowing family negotiations to remain the primary means of resolving inheritance disputes.

The study therefore argues that improving women's inheritance rights requires a multidimensional approach. Legal reforms alone are unlikely to produce meaningful change unless accompanied by efforts to transform family attitudes toward women's property ownership, strengthen legal awareness, simplify administrative procedures, and improve access to effective legal remedies. Community-based awareness initiatives involving families, religious scholars, legal professionals, and local institutions may contribute to reducing the gap between legal entitlement and actual implementation.

This research contributes to the growing literature on women's property rights by demonstrating that inheritance disputes should be understood not merely as legal issues but as family processes in which power, emotion, and social relationships shape economic outcomes. By placing family dynamics at the centre of analysis, the study offers a more nuanced understanding of why women continue to experience barriers in exercising inheritance rights despite comprehensive legal recognition. It also provides evidence that future policy interventions should address both institutional reform and intra-family decision-making if women's inheritance rights are to become a practical reality rather than a formal legal guarantee.

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